

Reproductive Cloning

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Introduction

The term cloning describes a number of different processes that can be used to produce genetically identical copies of a biological entity. It refers to the transfer of somatic cell's nucleus into an ovum, which then grows into an embryo. The copied material, which has the same genetic makeup as the original, is referred to as a clone. Reproductive cloning is defined as the deliberate production of genetically identical individuals. Each newly produced individual is a clone of the original. Monozygotic (identical) twins are natural clones. Clones contain identical sets of genetic material in the nucleus of every cell in their bodies. Thus, cells from two clones have the same DNA and the same genes in their nuclei. All cells, including eggs, also contain some DNA in the energy-generating "factories" called mitochondria. These structures are in the cytoplasm, the region of a cell outside the nucleus. Mitochondria contain their own DNA and reproduce independently. *True clones* have identical DNA in both the nuclei and mitochondria, although the term *clones* are also used to refer to individuals that have identical nuclear DNA but different mitochondrial DNA.

Do clones ever occur naturally?

Yes. In nature, some plants and single-celled organisms, such as bacteria, produce genetically identical offspring through a process called asexual reproduction. In asexual reproduction, a new individual is generated from a copy of a single cell from the parent organism. Natural clones, also known as identical twins, occur in humans and other mammals. These twins are produced when a fertilized egg splits, creating two or more embryos that carry almost identical DNA. Identical twins have nearly the same genetic makeup as each other, but they are genetically different from either parent.

How is reproductive cloning done?

Reproductive cloning is defined as the deliberate production of genetically identical individuals. There are two methods which are used to make live-born mammalian clones. Both require

implantation of an embryo in a uterus and then a normal period of gestation and birth. However, reproductive human or animal cloning is not defined by the method used to derive the genetically identical embryos suitable for implantation. The two methods used for reproductive cloning thus far are as follows:

1. Cloning using somatic cell nuclear transfer (SCNT): This procedure starts with the removal of the chromosomes from an egg to create an enucleated egg. The chromosomes are replaced with a nucleus taken from a somatic (body) cell of the individual or embryo to be cloned. This cell could be obtained directly from the individual, from cells grown in culture, or from frozen tissue. The egg is then stimulated, and in some cases, it starts to divide. If that happens, a series of sequential cell divisions leads to the formation of a blastocyst, or pre-implantation embryo. The blastocyst is then transferred to the uterus of an animal. The successful implantation of the blastocyst in a uterus can result in its further development, culminating sometimes in the birth of an animal. This animal will be a clone of the individual that was the donor of the nucleus. Its nuclear DNA has been inherited from only one genetic parent.

The number of times that a given individual can be cloned is limited theoretically only by the number of eggs that can be obtained to accept the somatic cell nuclei and the number of females available to receive developing embryos. If the egg used in this procedure is derived from the same individual that donates

Figure 1: Cloning by SCNT

the transferred somatic nucleus, the result will be an embryo that receives all its genetic material—nuclear and mitochondrial—from a single individual. That will also be true if the egg comes from the nucleus donor's mother, because mitochondria are inherited maternally. Multiple clones might also be produced by transferring identical nuclei to eggs from a single donor. If the somatic cell nucleus and the egg come from different individuals, they will not be identical to the nuclear donor because the clones will have somewhat different mitochondrial genes. Although this process has been used to successfully clone many different species of animals—including sheep, cows, mules, rabbits, and dogs—its success rate is low, with only a small percentage of embryos surviving to birth. Cloned animals that survive to birth also appear to age and die prematurely. This is because their DNA comes from adult cells that have undergone telomere shortening—loss of a small portion of the protective ends of chromosomes with each cell division—as part of the normal aging process.

While the chromosomal DNA of the clone is the same as that of the nucleus donor, it may have

different mitochondrial DNA, since the mitochondria come from the cytoplasm of the egg cell, which is usually from a different animal. Also, phenotypic differences can occur between the clone and the original animal, due to environmental and epigenetic factors.

2. Cloning by embryo splitting: This procedure begins with in vitro fertilization (IVF): the union of a sperm and an egg to generate a zygote, outside the woman's body. The zygote (from here onwards also called an embryo) divides into two and then four identical cells. At this stage, the cells can be separated and allowed to develop into separate but identical blastocysts, which can then be implanted in a uterus. The limited developmental potential of the cells means that the procedure cannot be repeated, so embryo splitting can yield only two identical mice and probably no more than four identical humans.

The DNA in embryo splitting is contributed by germ cells from two individuals—the mother who contributed the egg and the father who contributed the sperm. Thus, the embryos, like those formed naturally or by standard IVF, have two parents. Their mitochondrial DNA is identical, because this method of cloning is identical with the

natural formation of monozygotic twins and, in rare cases, even quadruplets.

Figure 2: Cloning by Embryo Splitting

Conclusion

Cloned mammalian animals can be made by replacing the chromosomes of an egg cell with a nucleus from the individual to be cloned, followed by stimulation of cell division and implantation of the resulting embryo. Cloned individuals, whether born at the same or different times, will not be physically or behaviorally identical with each other at comparable ages. Reproductive cloning can be done by two methods: Using somatic cell nuclear transfer (SCNT); by embryo splitting. Reproductive cloning may enable researchers to make copies of animals with the potential benefits including the production of genetically identical research animals, livestock with desired traits, and offspring of endangered species.

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